

THE ROLE OF BRAND SUITABILITY IN MODERATING ENDORSER CREDIBILITY ON INTENTION TO BUY

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Abstract

This research aims to explain the relationship between endorser credibility and brand attitude, as well as its relationship with brand purchase intentions. Data collection was carried out online for Indonesian people who like celebrities (Amanda Manopo and Renatta Moeloek). Data collected from 304 respondents was analyzed using Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The results show that endorser credibility and brand attitude have a positive relationship, brand attitude to brand purchase intentions have a positive relationship, and brand-endorser to brand purchase intentions have a positive relationship. Brand-endorser congruence does not positively moderate the relationship between endorser credibility and brand attitude, endorser credibility and brand purchase intention, and brand attitude and brand purchase intention. This means that the better the quality of brand congruence, the less it will affect endorser credibility, brand attitude, and brand purchase intentions. This research also discusses the quadratic effect and its implications for future research.

Keywords: Attitude, Brand Congruence, Cookware, Credibility Endorser, And Intention to Buy.

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between endorsers and follower behavior in purchasing brands advertised by endorsers is an interesting issue to study. The large use of a celebrity endorser in advertising is based on a phenomenon that is currently being developed. Celebrity is one of the most effective appeals to advertise a brand. Marketers take advantage of celebrities as advertising stars because of their large number of followers. The hope is that the use of celebrities as ad stars can influence their followers to grow purchase intentions of the advertised products. Some of the studies that are used as reasons for conducting this research are cookware advertisements. The advertisement shows the endorser using one of the cookware when cooking, this causes the endorser's followers to follow along using cookware with the same brand.

Some of the brands that can be mentioned here are brands from Cookware. One of the well-known cookware brands is Cookware Cypruz. The ad star used by Cookware Cypruz is Amanda Manopo. Cypruz Cookware is a product of kitchen and household appliances in Indonesia, designed using modern and simple technology that makes cooking activities in the kitchen easy, healthy, safe, and comfortable. The reason for choosing Amanda Manopo for this product is because the target market for this product is housewives. Currently, Amanda Manopo is the most popular celebrity among housewives, along with

her role in one of the electronic cinemas in Indonesia whose trends are increasing, this is shown in the graph displayed on Google Trends in the last twelve months. In the tabloid star Amanda Manopo, formerly a teen idol, now she is now loved by her mother. Thus, Amanda Manopo is considered an advertisement star according to the target market of Cookware Cypruz which takes advantage of Amanda Manopo's fame in the minds of housewives.

The second is a cookware ad starring Renatta Moeloek. Cookware is starring Renatta Moeloek, namely Cookware Supra. Cookware Supra is a cookware set made from a combination of stainless steel and Teflon which is deliberately designed with an anti-rust coating, which is easy to clean and safe when used to cook various foods. The target market for this product is housewives. The reason for this product using Renatta Moeloek as the star of its advertisement is because currently, Renatta Moeloek is a cook that many millennial mothers like. The graph displayed on Google Trends in the last twelve months, shows fans who have continued to increase. Thus, using Renatta Moeloek as an advertisement star is considered the right choice of advertisement star for Cookware Supra because the fans and followers of Renatta Moeloek will also use the same products used by Renatta Moeloek.

Of the two cases that have been put forward, the star of the Cypruz Cookware advertisement, who is an actress, model, singer, and entrepreneur, is Amanda Manopo. Amanda Manopo has a lot of followers on Instagram. Her followers on Instagram number 15.3 million. Meanwhile, the star of the Cookware Supra ad is a cook and restaurateur, namely Renatta Moeloek. Renatta Moeloek has 2.6 million followers on Instagram. The hope is that by using Amanda Manopo and Renatta Moeloek as commercial stars, the fans and followers of Amanda Manopo and Renatta Moeloek will also use the products used by Amanda Manopo.

So from the two cases of the cookware ad star, it can be seen how the role of celebrities in the promotion of a product. Celebrities have the power to invite their fans or followers to consume the same products as the products consumed by these celebrities. However, this still needs to be proven by testing or research that can provide accurate evidence. The previous research, namely research conducted by Molelekeng and Dondolo (2021), entitled The Effect of Celebrity Endorser Attributes on Purchase Intentions in South Africa. This study examines the effect of endorser characteristics on purchase intentions in South Africa. The sampling survey used South Africans living in Gauteng Province, totaling 145 respondents with an age range of 18 to 55 years. The results obtained from this study indicate that respondents see advertisements featuring celebrities. It can also be concluded that the results of the study indicate that consumer behavior such as purchase intention is influenced by attractiveness. However, in this study, expertise and trustworthiness are not related to purchase intention. Thus, understanding the attributes of celebrity endorsers can help organizations determine the most successful marketing strategies to be able to attract new potential customers and retain existing customers.

Another research that has previously been conducted is by Parmara, Manna, and Ghumanb (2020), entitled *The Impact of Celebrity Endorsers as In-store Stimulation on Impulse Purchases*. This research was conducted in India, by analyzing how celebrity endorsers in POP (point of purchase) advertisements affect consumers' impulsive purchases, both in the case of high-involvement and low-involvement products. In addition, it also examines the effect of compatibility between celebrities and products on consumer impulse purchases. An experimental study was conducted to collect data for six different situations using a sample of 218 students in India. The results obtained from this study indicate that the presence of celebrity endorsers in POP advertisements increases consumer impulse purchases. Additionally, celebrity endorsers were more effective in the case of high-involvement products than low-involvement products and celebrity fit to product category also influenced impulse buying, but only in the case of high-involvement products. This study contributes to the celebrity endorsement and impulse buying literature by finding the influence of celebrity endorsers on consumer impulse purchases. These findings are especially relevant to retailers and marketers interested in impulse buying, suggesting other ways to influence consumer impulse buying.

From the two studies above, further research will be better if it focuses on the credibility of the endorser. Focusing on the credibility of the endorser itself will be very beneficial for a brand. The advantage of a brand can be obtained by presentation from the endorser where the message conveyed can be trusted regarding the truth conveyed in the message of an advertisement. Thus, the message in an advertisement will be more easily accepted by the target market. Inference in purchases is an important variable to observe. This is one part of the consumption behavior component of a product. Schiffman and Kanuk (2008), argued that a purchase intention is a psychological aspect that has a considerable influence on behavior. Besides that, intention can also be a source of motivation that will direct a person to carry out an action or activity. On the other hand, intention is also an accurate predictor of actual behavior. This predictor can be used to predict how a person's behavior will be in the future.

In this study, the credibility of the endorser is a stimulus that can be conceptualized. This is in line with what was stated by Marla, Thomas, and Ellen (2002) where the credibility of the endorser is a positive characteristic of the communicator that influences the recipient of the message from the receiver. Thus, many marketers take advantage of fans and fanatical followers of a celebrity, so that these fans and followers also follow whatever the celebrity does or consumes. The behavior described is complex. According to the *Bigear Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI)*, the behavior itself is one of the reactions or one of the responses of each individual to the environment or stimuli. Meanwhile, according to Widyastika (2016), complex behavior is a behavior that involves several activities in a person's life, especially social activities.

It can be concluded that almost all brands can use individuals to become brand endorsers, hoping that their followers will follow the endorser manifested in purchase intentions. However, the significant level of this relationship still requires further research because

there is no conceptual opinion from previous studies that have been carried out. Under these conditions, it can underlie research and provide great research opportunities to create a concept for research objects in Indonesia. The model developed in this study relies on behavioral theory which can apply the influence of endorser credibility on purchase intentions with behavioral variables as moderation. Thus, this study aims to explain the influence of endorser credibility on purchase intentions through behavior.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This research is used to explain behavioral processes that begin with a cognitive construct in the form of individual perceptions of external stimuli, then the output of this cognitive structure leads to an emotional construct in the form of emotions in general. In the form of behavior, the process that ultimately animates the structure formed in the form of intention to behave, this is based on a cognitive psychology approach (Verbeke, 2001; Cook et al., 2002; Haryanto et al., 2015). The cognitive structure is expressed in terms of the credibility of the appeal due to individual perceptions of brand promotion. Individual perceptions of the program are assessed on the credibility, attractiveness, and expertise of the program itself. The results of this perception then influence the behavior towards the brand as an affective construct and the result of this behavior influences the purchase intention towards the brand. This study conceptualizes similarity as a regulatory factor (Kamins, 1990; Choi & Rifon, 2012a). This means that if individuals perceive a high level of conformity between brand segments it will further strengthen the process of forming brand behavior and purchase intentions, whereas if the level of similarity between brand segments is weak it will weaken the process. In this study, the application of a cognitive conceptualization approach in the formation of behavior and brand intentions is influenced by program attractiveness (Kahle & Homer, 1985).

The credibility of the endorser according to Marla, Thomas, and Ellen (2002) where the credibility of the endorser itself is one of the positive characteristics of the communicator that can influence the recipient of the message from the receiver. An important factor in ensuring effectiveness in conveying messages is using the credibility of the endorser. Celebrities who have credibility can produce good changes by encouraging changes in one's behavior. In addition, it also can influence followers to increase advertising and purchase of these products. In advertisements, respondents will consider whether to believe or not to believe the truth contained in the message content in the advertisement. This is one of the factors influenced by the credibility of the endorser.

According to Goldsmith, Lafferty, and Newell (2002), credibility itself is a level of trust from consumers to sources that provide information. Three dimensions can shape the credibility of the endorser. The first dimension is attractiveness, where an endorser who has allure will be more able to encourage his followers' buying intentions. The second is the level of trust, this dimension is a key characteristic in the effectiveness of conveying the message that the carrier of the message can be trusted. The last is expertise, where a communicator is considered a source that brings true and trustworthy statements in conveying the contents of the message in the advertisement. Several studies have shown

that the use of endorsers as an advertising tool has proven effective in influencing consumer behavior to buy these products (Choi and Rifon Hung et al., 2011; Knott and St. James, 2003; Taillon et al., 2020). Each endorser has a different appeal and several references explain that the attractiveness of a program's credibility does not only come from the physical aspect, but also from the aspects of similarity, familiarity, and liking (McGuire, 1985). Dimensions of Credibility, Attractiveness, and Expertise (Ohanian, 1990). Dexterity, Personality, Lifestyle (Endogun, 1999), Appearance, Personality, Likes, Similarities (Solomon, 2018). This study conceptualizes credibility as an individual's perception of the credibility of a program, which consists of the dimensions of credibility, attractiveness, and expertise. This concept was adapted from several studies that tested the effectiveness of the credibility program consisting of these three dimensions in influencing brand attitudes and purchase intentions (Dirks and Ferrin, 2001; Hussain et al., 2020). Thus, the use of celebrities in advertisements can stimulate changes in the behavior of consumers and foster purchase intentions.

Credibility is the first dimension that is considered dominant for celebrity credibility (Mayer et al., 1995). Celebgram gets a lot of followers because of its credibility. In this context, the endorser must be able to develop into a trustworthy person. This is because it implies high skill, compassion, and honesty (Dirks and Ferrin, 2001). This means that highly reliable people assure others that they can pursue what they are doing without feeling too risky. Most famous endorsers are respected by their followers because they rely on their expertise and know exactly how to attract customers for the advertised brand (Hussain et al., 2020).

Attractiveness is the next dimension in which individual ratings measure program credibility. The attractiveness of the program is one of the elements of the attractiveness of the program that makes it different from other programs. Each follower is perceived differently when the same brand is promoted by different celebrities. Brands with different appeals have different followers, which influence brand sales. Ohanian (1990) developed a scale to assess the success of celebrities in influencing their followers. Known as the Sumer Ohanian Credibility Model, this model identifies three main factors that contribute to program credibility (attraction, credibility, and expertise). In this model, program attractiveness becomes the focus of research. In various studies, program attractiveness is the most widely used variable to describe the program's role in persuading followers to buy advertised products, and this argument is based on attractiveness. This is supported by research by McGuire (1985) which shows that good looks explain purchase. Emphasize intent, not an eye-catching brand (Kahle and Homer, 1985; see also Huang et al., 2011).

Selegrams with more reliable expertise than those that do not affect their followers' preference for the program. This expected follower response is followed by a willingness to use the product as advertised in their favorite program (Andersen and Clevenger, 1963). Several researchers have shown that individuals are more likely to agree with programmers who are experts in their fields than those who are perceived as non-experts, indicating that followers are (Horai et al., 1974; (Chaiken), 1979, 1980; Ratneshwar and

Chaiken, 1991). Knowledge tested. Attitudes toward energy bar brands have been found to benefit from the knowledge of celebrity endorsers (Till and Busler, 2000). In fictional clothing company settings, they are talking avatars seen as experts have been shown to lead to increased brand satisfaction and brand attitudes (Sung and Kim, 2010). According to Martensen et al. (2018), The more knowledge a fashion brand influencer has, the more attractive it is.

Purchase intention according to Engel, Roger, and Paul (2001), is one of the subjective judgments about an item or service that will later be consumed by consumers. What is thought in the minds of consumers, to be purchased in the future is also a purchase intention. According to Schiffman and Kanuk (2000), intention is one of the internal factors that exist in individuals and will influence how consumers behave in the future. Intention is also one of the forms of thought that occurs from behavior that is reflected in a purchase plan to buy one or several products within a certain period. A desire to be involved in certain behaviors, namely where a consumer's buying behavior in the future can be seen from purchase intentions. According to Fazekas, Seen, and Ledgerwood (2001), measurement of purchase intention can be made before the purchase is made. This makes the prediction of purchase intention in certain cases less accurate. On the other hand, the strength of the relationship and the accuracy in predicting a purchase intention can vary depending on a) the specificity of the purchase intention, b) the novelty of the product, c) the size of the specific purchase intention, and d) the time between measure of behavior and intention. Thus, purchase intention can be used effectively as a predictor of a consumer's buying behavior.

Based on the research conducted, the results obtained mostly confirm the positive relationship between program reliability and positive attitudes toward brand purchase intentions (1985; Kamins, 1990; Onu et al., 2019). Various model developments were carried out to describe the performance concept more concretely about trust in terms of the desired trust. Frisby (2006) places more emphasis on racial attractiveness associated with celebrity skin color. The study explains that light-skinned celebrities are more trustworthy than dark-skinned celebrities. Furthermore, Morimoto and Chang (2009) examined proponents of Western and Japanese breeds which are considered more reliable than Japanese breeds (see also Morimoto, 2018). Similarly, Halim and Kiatkawsin (2021) published other research supporting racial beliefs. They examined whether the Korean program had high credibility among programs from other countries. The term Hallyu has emerged very high in the international entertainment world, especially in Indonesia. At this point, it can be said that celebrity credibility has become a stereotype for certain brands that profit from advertising programs (Dion et al., 1972; Frisby, 2006; Morimoto, 2018; Roozen and Raedts). 2015). Various studies also explain that people who can be trusted are preferred over those who cannot (Dion et al., 1972). This phenomenon underlies the emergence of the concept of good-looking communicators because they will get good attention and responses from the audience.

This study aims to explain the relationship between endorser credibility and brand attitude, as well as its relationship with brand purchase intention. Although many studies have found satisfactory test results on the relationship between program credibility and brand attitudes and brand purchase intentions (see Kahle and Homer, 1985; Kamins, 1990; (Halim and Kiatkaws-in, 2021), several other studies have found different things. i.e. there is no significant relationship between program credibility and brand attitude and brand purchase intention (Bower and Landreth, 2001; Phau and Lum, 2000; Pornpitakpan, 2003). This phenomenon provides empirical evidence that the effectiveness of screengrabs in shaping attitudes and brand purchase intentions still requires some testing so that its effectiveness in influencing the behavior of its followers gets evidence that can be accounted for.

For marketers, it is necessary to test the effectiveness of the program because several studies have found a non-significant relationship between the credibility of the program brand attitudes, and brand purchase intentions. In some cases, the celebrity role must be chosen based on the credibility relevance desired by followers, as explained three aspects need attention, namely credibility, charm, and expertise. This study attempts to explain program reliability from these three dimensions. Regarding the relationship between attitude and brand purchase intention, research supports a positive relationship between program credibility and brand attitude and brand purchase intention (Frisby, 2006; Halim and Kiatkawsin, 2021; Kumalasari, 2021). In other words, the higher the attractiveness of the program, the higher the positive attitude towards the brand. The following proposition is formulated, as follows:

H1: There is a positive relationship between endorser credibility and brand attitude.

H2: There is a positive relationship between endorser credibility and brand purchase intention.

Regarding the relationship between brand attitude and brand purchase intention, there are several references indicating a positive and significant relationship between brand attitude and brand purchase intention (Beneke et al., 2013; Setiawan Haryanto, 2014; Haryanto et al., 2019). This shows that the higher the attitude towards a brand, the higher the purchase intention towards that brand. This concept underlies the formulation of the following proposition:

H3: There is a positive relationship between brand attitude and brand purchase intention.

As previously mentioned, endorsers are people with a large number of followers. This is the basis for marketers using social media to promote their brand on certain social media. The fanaticism of these followers expects a positive response from these followers towards advertised products (Kahle and Homer, 1985; Onu et al., 2019; Sims, 2012). However, some studies show otherwise. This means that individuals respond positively to products advertised through the program only if the product is consistent with the program itself (Bower and Landreth, 2001; Phau and Lum, 2000; Pornpitakpan, 2003).

For individual followers looking at each program, it has varying degrees of credibility. It relies on the credibility, attractiveness, and expertise of a particular program, evaluated negatively (von-Mettenheim and Wiedmann, 2021). This phenomenon is the background to the emergence of the concept of brand-segment alignment. This concept explains that advertised brands should be perceived as consistent with celebrity credibility. This opinion contradicts the idea that physical attractiveness alone is not as important as influencing individual behavior without considering another aspect, namely brand-segment matching.

Various studies have shown that brand-endorser alignment is a variable that influences the process of forming positive attitudes and brand purchase intentions (Kamins and Gupta, 1994; Schouten et al., 2020). This means that convergence plays a key role in strengthening or weakening the process of forming attitudes and brand purchase intentions. If the individual feels that the high compatibility between the brand and the endorser has an impact on the process of forming attitudes and aspects that strengthen purchase intentions towards the brand, on the contrary, if the individual feels that the compatibility between the brand and the endorser is low, the purchase influences the formation of attitudes and aspects that improves the brand process. weaken intention. This discussion forms the basis for formulating the following propositions:

H4: There is a positive relationship between brand-endorser and brand purchase intention

H5: Square of brand-endorser and brand purchase intention

H6: Brand-endorser congruence positively moderates the relationship between endorser credibility and brand purchase intention.

The role of brand-endorser congruence in the relationship between brand attitudes and brand purchase intentions is based on the argument that individuals who like a brand do not necessarily intend to buy the brand when they perceive that the admired brand has no suitability when advertising the promoted brand (see Phau & Lum, 2000; Pornpitakpan, 2003). Here there is another aspect that plays a role in the form of an overly emotional individual attitude towards his favorite endorser. This study attempts to explain this phenomenon by conceptualizing the role of endorser brand alignment in moderating the relationship between brand attitudes and brand purchase intentions. The proposition is formulated, as follows:

H7: Brand-endorser congruence positively moderates the relationship between brand attitudes and brand purchase intentions.

METHODS

This research is focused on consumer purchase intention due to the influence of endorsers. Because this study was to test the external validity of the conceptualized model, the samples were taken from different populations. The population in this study were individual followers of endorser Amanda Manopo, who advertised Cypruz Cookware brand, and individual followers of endorser Renatta Moeloek, who advertised

Supra Brand Cookware. The population was taken 153 individual followers from endorser Amanda Manopo through an online survey. Meanwhile, 151 individuals were random followers of endorser Renatta Moeloek through an online survey as well. The implementation is by the researcher asking for the willingness of endorser followers and asking for their willingness to provide information as written on the questionnaire.

The survey was conducted using an online survey. The snowball technique is done by distributing a questionnaire to the celebrity's social media followers and spreading it to several friends in the WhatsApp group, asking them to share it with as many other individuals as possible, and so on for two months. To get a high response rate, five respondents were randomly selected as a reward in the form of credit worth Rp. 50,000. From the distribution of the questionnaires carried out, some respondents filled out the questionnaire completely and met the criteria. There were 304 (three hundred and four) respondents who filled out the questionnaire completely and met the criteria. Of the total respondents, there were 51 (fifty-one) respondents, or 16.78 percent of respondents who were male. There were 253 (two hundred and fifty-three) respondents or 83.22 percent of respondents who were female.

Of the total respondents, there were 3 (three) respondents, or 0.99 percent of respondents who had the last junior high school education. There were 40 (forty) respondents or 13.16 percent of respondents who had a high school education. Undergraduate education level is the highest respondent with a total of 248 (two hundred and forty-eight) respondents or 81.58 percent. And finally, 13 (thirteen) respondents had postgraduate education or 4.27 percent.

There were 178 (one hundred and seventy-eight) respondents or 58.55 percent of respondents who had incomes below IDR 1,500,000. There were 63 (sixty-three) respondents or 20.72 percent of respondents who had income between IDR 1,500,001 - IDR 2,500,000. The following data shows 38 (thirty-eight) respondents or 12.50 percent of respondents have an income between IDR 2,500,001 - IDR 3,500,000. Furthermore, there were 14 (fourteen) respondents, or 4.61 percent of respondents who had income between IDR 3,500,001 - IDR 4,500,000. Finally, there are 11 (eleven) respondents who have an income of more than IDR 4,500,000 or 3.62 percent.

The credibility of the endorser is an individual's perception of the ability of the endorser from the dimensions of trustworthiness, attractiveness, and expertise. Each dimension is explained with 5 indicators which are then measured with a 5-point Likert scale. Purchase intention is an individual's desire to buy a brand. This variable is explained by 5 indicators, which are then measured by a 5-point Likert scale. Consumer behavior is each individual's response to the environment or stimuli. This variable is explained by 5 indicators, then a 5-point Likert scale is measured.

The data analysis used in this study is using the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. PLS is a component- or variant-based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) model. They are using PLS-SEM through smart PLS software version 3.3.2. The analysis carried out includes validity, reliability, models, and hypothesis testing. The validity test is used to

measure the ability of the research instrument to measure its construct (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The instrument is considered valid if the value is at least 0.70. However, instruments that are between 0.40 and 0.70 can also be considered valid if they meet the minimum requirements of composite reliability (CR) and average variance extract (AVE) (Hair et al., 2016).

Furthermore, a reliability test was carried out to test the consistency of the instruments used in this study. It is also used to measure the extent to which the instrument is free from bias or error (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Reliable instruments are instruments that have a CR value greater than 0.70. Hypothesis testing was carried out using the bootstrap resampling procedure. The relationship between variables is determined using the path coefficient value. The positive relationship is determined by the value of the positive path coefficient and vice versa. The significance of the relationship, on the other hand, was determined using a p-value (accepted if $p < 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the validity test are obtained from the outer loading value of each indicator on Smart-PLS. Then the reliability test is carried out after the validity test is declared passed. Table 1 shows the outer loading, CR, and AVE values of each indicator. All indicators are reliable because they meet the following requirements: $CR > 0.70$ and $AVE > 0.50$ (Hair et al., 2016). The results of the validity test show that 4 indicators are invalid from the credibility of the endorser. Invalid indicators are AT4: There is nothing unattractive from the star celebrity who advertises the product, EX5: The advertisement becomes interesting because of the expertise of the celebrity presenting it, TR1: In my opinion, the celebrity star is seen to have honesty in advertising the product, and TR3: Words Celebrity stars look trustworthy in advertising products.

Table 1: Convergent Validity and Reliability Tests

Variable/indicator		Outer Loading	Cronbach Alpha	AVE
Attitude			0.890	0,694
ATT 1	I like the products advertised by celebgrams	0,834		
ATT 2	I welcome the products advertised by the celebrity	0,827		
ATT 3	I think positively about products advertised by celebgrams	0,806		
ATT 4	I enthusiastically welcome the products advertised by celebrities	0,873		
ATT 5	A product advertised by a celebrity is a good idea	0,825		
Brand Congruence			0.921	0,760
KR 1	There is a match between the celebrity and the product	0,864		
KR 2	Between the program and the advertised product it feels like	0,914		
KR 3	How harmonious it is between celebrities who star and advertise products	0,904		
KR 4	Celebrity stars look suitable for starring in advertised products	0,869		

KR 5	Celebgrams who star in advertisements seem to blend in with the advertised product	0,803		
Intention to Buy			0.922	0,762
PL 1	I will buy products advertised by celebgrams	0,907		
PL 2	I want to buy a product advertised by a celebrity	0,879		
PL 3	There is a tendency from me to buy advertised products	0,841		
PL 4	Chances are I will buy a product advertised by a celebrity	0,889		
PL 5	I will buy the advertised product in the future	0,847		
Credibility Endorser			0.928	0,500
AT 1	Celebrity stars look good in advertising products	0,748		
AT 2	Celebrity stars in advertisements are interesting to watch	0,743		
AT 3	Celebrity stars are pleasing to the eye in advertising products	0,716		
AT 5	Whatever is brought by celebrity stars looks interesting	0,731		
EX 1	Celebgrams who advertise products are seen to be in control of the advertised products	0,736		
EX 2	Celebgrams who advertise products can deliver the advertised products well	0,791		
EX 3	Selebgram has expertise in the advertised product	0,720		
EX 4	Celebgrams looks skilled in presenting advertised products	0,759		
TR 2	Celebgrams stars look sincere in advertising products	0,730		
TR 4	Celebgram stars look honest in advertising products	0,755		
TR 5	Celebgram stars' words in advertising products contain truth	0,723		

Note: CR>0,70 dan AVE>0,50

Furthermore, discriminant validity testing was conducted to explain the variables' relationship. The results showed that all variables met the discriminant validity requirements. That is, the relationship between the same variables is higher than the relationship between different variables. The hetero-trait-mono-trait ratio (HTMT) was used to evaluate discriminant validity (Table 2). Discriminant validity indicates that all constructs have satisfactory discriminant validity; each HTMT value does not exceed 0.85 (Voorhees et al., 2016). Thus it can be explained that the average response of respondents to all variables is relatively high, with the combined average value of these variables.

Table 2: Discriminant Validity

Variable/indicator	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4
Attitude	3,843	0,674	0,833			
Brand Congruence	3,922	0,666	0,638	0,872		
Intention to buy	3,532	0,820	0,674	0,482	0,873	
Credibility Endorser	3,659	0,644	0,762	0,725	0,511	0,707

Note: Diagonal italic value represents the HTMT value

The relationship between variables will be shown in Table 3. The relationship between endorser credibility and attitude is significant and positive, so hypothesis 1 is supported (Standard Coefficient = 0.762; SD = 0.036; $p = 0.000$). This shows that the better the quality of the endorser's credibility, the higher the brand attitude.

The results of subsequent tests show that there is no significant relationship between endorser credibility and intention to buy (Standard Coefficient = -0.124; SD = 0.094; $p = 0.190$), so hypothesis 2 is not supported. That is, the endorser's credibility is not a variable considered important by consumers in growing brand purchase intentions. The results of the next test show that there is a significant relationship between attitude and intention to buy (Standard Coefficient = 0.676; SD = 0.075; $p = 0.000$), so hypothesis 3 is supported.

That is, the better the quality of the brand attitude, the more it influences the brand purchase intention. The results of subsequent tests show that there is a significant relationship between brand congruence and intention to buy (Standard Coefficient = 0.147; SD = 0.070; $p = 0.037$), so hypothesis 4 is supported. That is, the better the quality of brand congruence, the more it influences the intention to buy the brand.

Table 3: Proposition Testing Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. dev.	T-stat	P-value
Credibility Endorser-Attitude	0,762	0,036	14,742	0,000
Credibility Endorser-Intention to Buy	-0,124	0,094	0,202	0,190
Attitude - Intention to Buy	0,676	0,075	8,351	0,000
Brand Congruence - Intention to Buy	0,147	0,070	0,967	0,037
Quadratic Effect 1 (Credibility Endorser – Intention to Buy)	0,017	0,031	0,068	0,583
Moderating Effect 2 (Credibility Endorser - Brand Congruence - Intention to Buy)	-0,050	0,049	0,100	0,302
Moderating Effect 3 (Attitude - Brand Congruence - Intention to Buy)	0,074	0,057	0,484	0,196

The test results further show that there is a quadratic effect regarding the relationship between endorser credibility and intention to buy (Standardized Coefficient = 0.017; SD = 0.031; $p = 0.583$), so hypothesis 5 shows that endorser credibility has a certain point that makes a product attractive to consumers, research shows that the endorser studied, who was initially unknown, at some point became known and became considered important by consumers in growing brand purchase intentions.

The results of the next test show that there is an insignificant relationship in the moderating effect between endorser credibility - brand congruence - intention to buy (Standardized Coefficient = -0.050; SD = 0.094; $p = 0.302$), so hypothesis 6 is not supported. This means that the better the quality of brand congruence, the less it will affect the endorser's credibility and brand purchase intentions. These test results are supported by test results which show weak results (f_2 at $\Delta R^2 = 0.004$) as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Results of interaction effects

Variable	R ² (in%)	f ²
Attitude - Intention to Buy	0,511	0,360
Brand Congruence - Intention to Buy	0,467	0,018
Credibility Endorser – Attitude	0,555	1,078
Credibility Endorser – Intention to Buy	0,467	0,009
Credibility Endorser - Brand Congruence - Intention to Buy	0,467	0,004
Attitude - Brand Congruence - Intention to Buy	0,511	0,008
Credibility Endorser – Intention to Buy	0,467	0,003

Further testing shows that there is an insignificant relationship in the moderating effect between attitude - brand congruence - intention to buy (Standardized Coefficient = 0.074; SD = 0.057; p = 0.196), so hypothesis 7 is not supported. This means that the better the quality of brand congruence, the less it affects brand attitudes and brand purchase intentions. These test results are supported by test results which show weak results (f² at delta R² = 0.008) as shown in Table 4.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTION

Based on the results of the data analysis performed, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between the credibility of the endorser and the brand attitude, thus it can be said that the better the quality of the credibility of the endorser, the influence on the brand attitude. There is also a significant relationship between brand attitudes and brand purchase intentions, thus it can be said that the better the quality of brand attitudes, the influence on brand purchase intentions.

The last significant relationship is the relationship between brand congruence and intention to buy. Thus it can be said that the better the quality of brand congruence, the more it influences the intention to buy the brand.

In addition to the results of the analysis which show a significant relationship, there is also an insignificant relationship. The results that show no significance are found in the relationship between the credibility of the endorser and the intention to buy the brand.

Thus, it can be said that the better the quality of the credibility of the endorser, it does not affect the intention to buy the brand. In addition, brand congruence congruence does not moderate positively the relationship between endorser credibility and brand purchase intention, thus it can be said that the better the quality of brand congruence, the less it affects the credibility of the endorser and the intention to purchase the brand.

The last insignificant result is that brand congruence does not moderate positively the relationship between attitudes towards the brand and brand purchase intention, thus it can be said that the better the quality of brand congruence, the better the attitude towards the brand and the intention to buy the brand.

Other results also show that there is a quadratic effect. This quadratic effect shows the relationship between endorser credibility and intention to buy.

The results show that the credibility of the endorser has a certain point that makes a product attractive to consumers. The results of this study indicate that the endorser understudy who was initially unknown, at some point because of being one of the stars in an event made this celebrity become known. After being known and becoming an idol, consumers consider becoming a celebrity important in cultivating purchase intentions for whatever brand they use.

The author proposes several suggestions to improve further research. Suggestions were made based on the results of checking question items from an average of 304 respondents. The average score of each question item that does not meet the convergent validity requirements with an outer loading value below 0.7 will be given suggestions as a consideration.

The suggestions that will be given are as follows:

- 1) From the attractiveness group, regarding the question "There is nothing unattractive from celebrity stars who advertise products". It turns out that this question has an outer loading value below 0.7, this is because not all celebrity stars who advertise products are interesting, so companies must sort out which celebrity stars are the most suitable, not just from their fame to get celebrity stars that can attract when advertising a product.
- 2) From the expertise group, regarding the question "advertising is interesting because of the expertise of the celebrity presenter". This question has an outer loading value below 0.7, this is because not all celebrity stars can attractively package advertisements, so companies must sort out which celebrity stars are the most suitable not only for their fame so that advertisements can be classed as attractive as possible with the expertise of celeb gram star itself.
- 3) From the trustworthiness group, regarding the question "in my opinion, celebrity stars appear to have honesty in advertising products". This question has an outer loading value below 0.7, this is because not all of these celebrity stars have a good image, so they don't necessarily say honestly and sincerely when advertising a product. So companies have to sort out which celebrity stars are the most suitable, not just based on their fame so that when advertising a product, it can inspire and feel like you are using the product.
- 4) From the trustworthiness group, regarding the question "celebgram star's words look trustworthy in advertising products". This question has an outer loading value below 0.7, this is because not all celebrity stars who advertise products are interesting, so companies must sort out which celebrity stars are the most suitable not only for their fame so that the advertisements delivered are more natural and it is believable that the celeb star uses the same product.

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